

CHALKONES DERIVED FROM QUINACETOPHENONE

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Quinacetophenone has been condensed with various aldehydes to yield the corresponding polyhydroxy chalkones. The optimum conditions for the condensation have been investigated. Some of these chalkones have been isomerised to the flavanones.

A good deal of work on the chalkones derived from resacetophenone, gallacetophenone and phloracetophenone and their ethers is available in literature (Russel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 218 *et seq.* cf. *Chem. Rev.*, 1935, 17, 155; Wheeler and co-workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 17, 37; 1938, 1320 *et seq.*; Lal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 296; Venkatraman *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 866). But very little work has been done on the chalkone formation from quinacetophenone though its derivatives are also widely distributed in nature. Kostanecki *et. al* (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 326; 1904, 37, 773) reported that quinacetophenone monoethyl or methyl ether condensed with various aldehydes to give flavanones directly. Later Russel (*loc. cit.*) tried to prepare chalkones by directly condensing the polyhydric ketones with aldehydes: only highly coloured products were obtained. To simplify matters, Russel and Clarke (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2652) used quinacetophenone dibenzoate with benzoyloxybenzaldehyde derivatives and succeeded in synthesising the benzoylated chalkones, using hydrochloric acid gas as the condensing agent. To obtain the hydroxy-chalkones, they devised a procedure for de-benzoylation which often led to a mixture of hydroxy-flavanone and chalkone.

In the present investigation, quinacetophenone has been condensed with various aldehydes, viz, benzaldehyde, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehydes, anisaldehyde, vanillin, etc., in presence of caustic potash solution (generally 40%). It is found that the chalkones are conveniently obtained in fairly good yields by proper adjustment of the experimental conditions, viz., concentration of alkali, period of reaction and temperature.

The effect of various factors like the concentration of alkali, period of reaction and temperature on the above chalkone formation has been investigated.

In most of the cases, the condensation was effected by using 40% alkali as the condensing agent. The use of lesser concentration generally reduced the yield of the chalkone. If the reaction mixture was heated previously on a water-bath for some time, the reaction was over within a shorter period, but the yield of the chalkone was considerably reduced, e.g. in case of benzaldehyde condensation. But in case of salicylaldehyde and vanillin, it was not affected by heating; the condensation could only be effected by keeping the reaction mixture for a fairly long period. In case of anisaldehyde and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, longer period of reaction did not favour the condensation, but the previous heating on a water-bath was found to be necessary.

It is noteworthy that *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde did not yield a trace of chalcone; it always led to the direct formation of the corresponding flavanone. The chalcones derived from salicylaldehyde, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde and vanillin have been isomerised to their respective flavanones by means of dilute HCl solution (3%). Various functional derivatives of the chalcones have been prepared.

The chalcones described here give blood-red coloration with concentrated sulphuric acid and dissolve in alkali producing red or orange solution; with alcoholic ferric chloride most of them give reddish brown coloration.

In spite of several attempts, protocatechuic aldehyde, *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde and α - and β -naphthaldehydes did not undergo the condensation.

It will be interesting to note that the chalcones described in this paper did not yield any definite bromo derivatives, when treated with bromine under various conditions, only pasty mass was obtained.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Quinacetophenone required for the purpose of this investigation was prepared by the Fries migration of quinol diacetate according to Amin and Shah (under publication in *Org. Syn.*, 1948; see also this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 377).

2:5-Dihydroxychalcone.—Caustic potash solution (20 c.c., 40%) was gradually added to a solution of quinacetophenone (3 g.) and benzaldehyde (3 g.) in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) with shaking. The reaction mixture was then left at room temperature for 7 days with occasional shaking. The colour of the solution changed from dark green to red. It was then diluted with water (250 c.c.) and acidified with dilute HCl (1:1). A greenish yellow solid slowly separated; it was collected and crystallised from alcohol as orange-yellow needles, m.p. 215°, yield 2.0 g. (Found: C, 74.9; H, 5.2. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.0 per cent). The chalcone is soluble in all common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in benzene and petroleum ether.

The above condensation was investigated under different conditions.

The *acetyl derivative* was prepared by acetic anhydride-pyridine method (refluxing on a water-bath for 4-5 hours), and crystallised from acetic acid in colorless, flat prisms, m. p. 108°. (Found: C, 70.0; H, 5.0. $C_{15}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 70.3; H, 4.9 per cent).

The *benzoyl derivative* was prepared similarly using benzoyl chloride and crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow prisms, m. p. 129°. (Found: C, 78.1; H, 4.5. $C_{20}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 77.7; H, 4.5 per cent).

The *methoxy derivative* was prepared by dimethyl sulphate in alkaline solution and crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m. p. 124°. (Found: C, 76.2; H, 5.6. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 76.1; H, 6.0 per cent).

2:5:2'-Trihydroxychalkone.—Potassium hydroxide (20 c.c., 40%) was gradually added with shaking to a cooled solution of quinacetophenone (3 g.) and salicylaldehyde (3 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.). The reaction mixture was then kept at room temperature for 7 days with occasional shaking and worked up as before. The orange solid obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol as red needles, m. p. 190-92°, yield 1.9 g. (Found: C, 70.2; H, 4.5. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 70.3; H, 4.7 per cent). The chalkone is soluble in alcohol, acetic acid and nitrobenzene but insoluble in chloroform benzene and petrol ether. Russel (*loc. cit.*) could not get this chalkone from the de-benzoylated product.

The *acetyl derivative* was prepared by acetic anhydride-sodium acetate method and crystallised from alcohol in prisms, m. p. 102°. (Found: C, 65.8; H, 4.6. $C_{21}H_{18}O$ requires C, 66.0; H, 4.7 per cent).

The *benzoyl derivative* was prepared by benzoyl chloride-pyridine method as before and crystallised from acetic acid in brown microcrystalline powder, m. p. 139°. Russel and Clarke give the same m. p.

6:2'-Dihydroxyflavanone.—A hot solution of 2:5:2'-trihydroxychalkone (0.5 g.) in absolute alcohol (40 c.c.) was treated with dilute hydrochloric acid (70-80 c.c., 3%) till a permanent turbidity appeared. Enough alcohol was then added to get a clear solution, which was refluxed on a water-bath for 24 hours. It was then concentrated when a dark brown solid separated; it was repeatedly extracted with benzene as white clusters of needles, m. p. 176°. Russel and Clarke isolated this flavanone from the debenzoylated mixture. They report its m. p. as 178°.

6:3'-Dihydroxyflavanone.—The condensation of quinacetophenone (3 g.) with *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (3 g.) was effected as before using potassium hydroxide (10 c.c., 80%) solution, leaving it at room temperature for 24 hours. The product obtained was crystallised from alcohol as faint yellow needles, m. p. 240°, identical with Russel and Clarke's flavanone (*loc. cit.*), yield 1.6 g. (Found: C, 70.2; H, 4.5. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$: C, 70.3; H, 4.7 per cent). It gives no characteristic coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. It is soluble in alcohol, acetic acid and nitrobenzene, but insoluble in benzene, chloroform and petrol ether.

The above condensation was investigated under different conditions but only the flavanone could be isolated.

The *benzoyl derivative* was crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow crystals, m. p. 104°. (Found: C, 74.6; H, 4.0. $C_{20}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 75.0; H, 4.3 per cent).

2:5:4'-Trihydroxychalkone.—A solution of quinacetophenone (3 g.) and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (3 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) was treated with caustic potash solution (40 c.c., 40%) with shaking and cooling. The reaction mixture was then refluxed on a water-bath for 15 to 20 minutes till it turned dark red. The product, isolated as before, crystallised from glacial acetic acid as reddish yellow prisms, m. p. 223-25°, yield 1.7 g. (Russel and Clarke give m. p. 222-24°). The chalkone is soluble in alcohol, acetic acid and sparingly soluble in chloroform, benzene and petrol ether.

The *benzoyl* derivative was crystallised from alcohol as microcrystalline pale yellow solid, m.p. 142°. (Found: C, 75.8; H, 4.1. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{24}O_7$: C, 76.0; H, 4.2 per cent). Russel and Clarke (*loc. cit.*) report m.p. 136°.

6: *4'-Dihydroxyflavanone*.—The above chalcone was isomerised by dilute HCl as before. The flavanone crystallises from alcohol as pale yellow needles, m.p. 230°. (Found: C, 70.1; H, 4.2. $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 70.3; H, 4.7 per cent).

2: *5-Dihydroxy-4'-methoxychalcone*.—A mixture of quinacetophenone (3 g.), anisaldehyde (3 g.), alcohol (20 c.c.) and potassium hydroxide (20 c.c., 40%) was heated on a water-bath for 25 to 30 minutes and then left at room temperature for 24 hours and worked up as before. The product obtained crystallised from alcohol (animal charcoal) as orange needles, m.p. 178-80°, yield 1.7 g. (Found: C, 70.8; H, 4.9. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 71.1; H, 5.2 per cent). It is easily soluble in alcohol and acetic acid but sparingly soluble in benzene, chloroform and nitrobenzene and insoluble in petrol ether.

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from glacial acetic acid as pale yellow granules, m.p. 130°. (Found: C, 67.5; H, 4.8. $C_{20}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 67.8; H, 5.1 per cent).

The *benzoyl* derivative was crystallised from alcohol, as pale yellow micro-crystalline powder, m.p. 163°. (Found: C, 75.1; H, 4.5. $C_{30}H_{22}O_8$ requires C, 75.3; H, 4.6 per cent).

2: *5: 4'-Trihydroxy-3'-methoxychalcone*.—Quinacetophenone (3 g.) in alcohol (20 c.c.) was condensed with vanillin (3 g.) in presence of potassium hydroxide (20 c.c., 40%). The reaction mixture was left for 7 days at room temperature. It was worked up as usual. A solid slowly separated which was crystallised from dilute alcohol as violet needles, m. p. 176°, yield 1.5 g (Russel and Clarke give m. p. 173°). The chalcone is easily soluble in alcohol and acetic acid but sparingly soluble in chloroform and benzene.

The *acetyl* derivative was crystallised from benzene as pale yellow microcrystalline needles, m. p. 105°. (Found: C, 63.0; H, 4.5. $C_{22}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 64.1; H, 4.8 per cent).

The *benzoyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol as pale yellow, fine crystals, m.p. 147° (Russel and Clarke give the same m.p.).

The *methoxy* derivative was prepared by dimethyl sulphate-alkali method and crystallised from alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 127°. (Found: C, 69.3; H, 6.0. $C_{19}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 69.5; H, 6.1 per cent).

6: *4'-Dihydroxy-3'-methoxyflavanone*.—2: *5: 4'-Trihydroxychalcone* was isomerised to the corresponding flavanone as lustrous pale yellow needles from alcohol, m.p. 226°. (Found: C, 66.8; H, 4.5. $C_{16}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 67.1; H, 4.9 per cent).

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